

Implementing advance control strategies to improve the performance of a microgrid

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Oct 19, 2023

Revised Jul 3, 2024

Accepted Aug 7, 2024

Keywords:

Extreme learning machine

Microgrid

Power system stabilizer

Proportional-integral-derivative controller

Renewable energy sources

ABSTRACT

Integration of flexible and non-dispatchable renewable energy production will influence the operation and future expansion of prevailing power systems. Because of the variations in performance responses between microgrid (MG) and regular generators, including renewable energy sources-based (RES-based) MG into the electrical system may have an influence on stability analysis. The reduction in switching frequency induced by these energy processors electronic interconnected electricity producing sources has a detrimental impact on the system's structural analysis, potentially leading to stability issues. Power infusion from RES-based MG, on the other hand, increases damping efficiency, reducing transmission line congestion and power shortage. As a result, in light of expanded MG information, it is important to analyse more complex stability problems and regulate the production of a power grid. This study will examine the effect of RES-based MG on the structural analysis and controller of a multimachine multi-area device in various scenarios This paper defines the growth of a one-of-a-kind proportional-integral-derivative (PID-based) power system stabilizer (PSS) type2 fuzzy partial order based on a meta-heuristic hybrid technique for refining the efficiency and robustness of harmonic currents.

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1. INTRODUCTION

With an annual growth of 26% and a steady increase of about 12% through 2020, wind energy is the rapidly expanding renewable resource. The European Union (EU), for example, recently released energy targets and the new climate under the 2030 framework, which contains an EU-wide reach an agreement target of at least 27% by 2030 [1]. However, the profitability of these sources must be integrated into the present energy structures because they vary throughout the time and geographical locations [2], [3]. The universal denominator is that they are flexible and not disposable, which means that electricity may be produced differently and can't be programmed in the same manner as traditional generating capacity. The potential of incorporating such resources into accessible energy systems is determined by two primary influences: i) the production power of renewable energy plants' temporal variability and ii) the precision with which projections for variable production are made.

The aim of this study is to discuss previous studies on the assessment of temporal variability [4], [5]. We examine what is known about variation at particular websites and for greater groupings of control plants, with a general focus on the methods, processes, and models used to measure temporal flexibility variety. A slew of initiatives has been launched in recent years to reduce the impact of non-dispatchable infrastructure provides oscillation on the efficiency and reliability of electrical systems [6], [7]. Paraphrase that has been formalised One option is to switch to a more scalable power generation system based on conventional technologies with improved start and load-following competences [8], [9], and the generating park can accommodate a greater number of basic GT cycles [10]. Many options for energy storage systems (ES) are now available to solve the problems of growing the usage of renewable power [11]-[16]. Pumped-hydro-storage (PHS) plants are well known for their ability to easily balance power between them. However, the capacity to construct large hydro plants is restricted by the accessibility of appealing locations, which varies by geographic zone, as well as social acceptance concerns and environmental implications, so extremely large new hydro plant installations are not considered feasible in most countries in the medium term [17]. PHS established capacity in EU nations could hit 91-188 GW in the future (2050 horizon) contingent on the situation. This is due to new plant construction or repowering of the current fleet. (In Europe, the connected PHS capacity is about 40 GW [18], [19]. CAES is being considered as an alternative solution, and the device has been demonstrated in a few cases amid similar site availability problems McIntosh on short time scales, EES are ideal for frequency and voltage regulation. The wind turbine can operate at a variety of wind speeds, optimizing yearly energy output. The doubly fed induction generator (DFIG) rotor control strategy algorithm is utilized in GE wind energy generation's 750 kW and 1.5 MW turbine, as well as the 3.6 MW overseas versions [20].

In a variety of ways, using fuzzy logic to control wind driven DFIGs has proven to be efficient. Both active and reactive power generation is controlled using fuzzy logic [21]. The sole variable utilized as an input to the fuzzy structure was the error signal of the controlled variable. The erroneous signal from the controlled parameter is sent into any neuro-fuzzy gain tuner. Because of the evolving environment of the application, the wind-driven DFIG in this work was described using a 2-axis (direct and quadrature axes) dynamic mechanism model. Because saturation circumstances have such a large influence on application performance, induction machine modelling has accounted for both main flux and leakage flux saturation [22]. The computer prototype is then utilized to design and imitate a wind-driven DFIG device with neuro-fuzzy vector power using the machine model. A collection of regular proportional integral (PI) controllers with neuro-fuzzy gain schedulers is used to monitor the vectors. The neuro-fuzzy systems are optimised to deliver the finest energetic output when following the greatest PowerPoint curve of the wind turbine. To validate the measured findings, experiments were carried out on a 2 kW lab DFIG.

2. METHOD

2.1. Proposed type-2 fuzzy PID controller

Fractional calculus. The fundamental operator D of order q of non-integer order is deducted and incorporated using differential equations. The interpretation of Grunwald-Letnikov (GL) and Riemann-Liouville (RL) explanation is the two most common mathematical justifications of minuscule differentials integral.

$$D_h^q f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-q)} \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \int_l^h \frac{f(\tau)}{(t-\tau)^{q-n+1}} (d\tau) \quad t > h, n \in \mathbb{R}^+ \quad (1)$$

Fractional order proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controller. As an integrated order and discriminatory PID controller, a simpler PID controller may be extended to provide greater autonomy through integrated derivatives commands and enhanced efficiencies of operation. A controller's output signal may be expressed as (2):

$$G_c(S) = K_p + \frac{K_i}{s^\lambda} + K_d s^\mu \quad (\lambda, \mu \in \mathbb{R}) \quad (2)$$

2.2. Fractional order and type-2 hybridization PID control

The variables for input scaling (SF) are k_e and k_{ed} of this special design, whereas K_o and K_{oi} are increasingly fast-growing. As described in [23]-[25], this common control system has numerous benefits over a typical fuzzy-based PID controller. The enhanced fuzziness aids in the recovery of logically correct material. Negative medium, negative large, zero, positive medium, negative small, positive small, and positive high are the linguistic variables NL, NS, NM, ZR, PM, PS, and PL. Figure 1 depicts the proposed controller based on extreme learning machine (ELM). The scaling components of insignificant order fuzzy controllers k_e , k_{ed} , K_o , K_{oi} , and fractional order λ , μ should be optimised for the nominated power base and participation function during the design process.

Figure 1. MATLAB model of proposed ELM based controller

2.3. Formulation of the optimization problem

A secondary damping controller in a power system is designed to mitigate low-frequency oscillations produced by minor or major disruptions. The impact of these oscillations can be seen in line power, rotor speed, and power angle variations. Controller parameters can be optimized to lower an unbiased event that should represent maximal damping in order to effectively damp these oscillations. As a result, the purpose of the design problem is to obtain the shortest settling time and the least amount of overshoot for the system's deviations. The output index in this study that meets all of these criteria is the (ITAE) integral of simultaneous controls by the perceived worth of the mistake.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cooperation proposed by load frequency control (LFC) aims to decrease the switching frequency to zero as rapidly as feasible through regulating inputs DG, EVs, and virative inertia control (VIC). Simulated inertia is a component of VSG which is tested with RERs, random load variations and structure inertia varieties using a maximum power mechanism and digital over/under frequency relay (OUFR). In Figure 2, the suggested microgrid (MG) model is displayed.

The isolated MG frequency is simulated and analyzed based on many modifications in wind power production, solar power, household charges, system inertia, and MATLAB/Simulink parameters (i.e., uncertainties). In the attending of solar power and high wind fluctuations as well as load changes the islanded MG is measured throughout a simulated duration of 10 minutes. Three scenarios are used on the MG to examine the complex protection of the islanded MG using the proposed synchronization of controller and digital OUFR.

The primary purpose of this sector is an analysis of the MG output through the recommended synchronized approaches LFC, VIC, and OUFR, including three distinct degrees of inertia in wind, PV and charging variations. In the Table 1 various operating conditions of the MG are described. The different circumstances of disturbance are summarised during the reproduction.

3.1. Case 1

In this example, the MG in island is tested in system-level inertia and is enabled under all operational conditions. Thus, without the aid of a digital OUFR the directors regarding centre may be operated. The switching frequency climbs to 0.97 Hz with the connected wind farm without the use of a 20 second VIC and reaches 0.84 Hz with the usual VIC. The frequency shift for VIC dependent is just 0.34 Hz, and the term average scenario is restored within just 5 seconds, using the suggested improved controller parameters. In this situation, the suggested coordination is successful in maintaining dynamic protection of MGs contrasted with the case with or without the typical VIC.

3.2. Case 2

In this example, the MG system is put through its paces by decreasing the system inertia to 55% of its default value. The digital OUFR energy and a journey signal is sent to the circuit boom when the

industrial supply is applied of the integrate value (K) surpasses its threshold value at 150 seconds. In that instance, the traditional VIC, in conjunction with the main and LFC, maintains the device frequency within the permitted range. However, at 300 seconds after the wind connection, the frequency deviation increased to approximately 1.2 Hz. Figure 3 presents the frequency of solar array, ES, and generator of the system. The digital OUFER does not turn on at that point because (K) has not reached the fixed value and needs to be adjusted. As a result, the adjusted VIC-based optimal PID was effective in keeping frequency nonconformities within reasonable limits to nearly 0.44 Hz at the time of wind farm link in this extreme scenario.

Figure 2. MATLAB MG model

Table 1. The MG operates under a variety of situations

Source	Starting	Stopping	Size
Industrial load	150 s	-	0.22
Residential load	Initial	400 s	0.12
Wind power	300 s	-	0.26
PV	Initial	-	0.15

Figure 3. Frequency of solar array, ES, and generator

3.3. Case 3

With the inertia of the system decreased to 35% of default inertia, instability of the MG system becomes quite problematic. As a result, the OUF_R provides system protection after 150 seconds after the first interruption by sending an indication to the power supplies to control the producing units. The OUF_R is enabled when two conditions occur: the device frequency exceeds the limits, and the integrator performance exceeds the limit (K). As a result, the OUF_R sends a trip signal that responds rapidly, protecting the equipment from failure.

Figure 4 demonstrates the fractional-order integrator’s (P(s)) step responses for various approaches. The MG controller includes six different algorithms to help minimise the generation cost of all the pricing methods. There are six MG control algorithms: DI (various layers), grey wolf optimizer (GWO), modified gray wolf optimizer (MGWO), micro gap wire chambers (MGWC), and MGWSA. Size of the screen var={parameters: a displays the variable and fixed variables for all methods in Table 2} used to try to minimise the value of the objective feature. The MG system is presented in Table 2, along with its historical and forecasted generation costs and characteristics.

Figure 4. The fractional-order integrator’s (P(s)) step responses for various approaches

Table 2. Parameters

Algorithms	Parameters	Tunable parameters
ELM	Population size=80	Crossover ratio=0.7 Mutation factor=.25 A varies from 2 to 0 wmax=0.9; wmin=0.6; c1=2; c2=2
	Maximum iteration=500	a varies from 2 to 0 AP varies from 1 to 0 fl=2 a varies from 2 to 0 AP varies from 1 to 0 fl=2
	Charging, discharging efficiencies of ESS	0.95
	Tie-line capacity for MG k to purchase/sell energy from/to the remaining MGs	1,000 kW

Four fault disturbance scenarios are evaluated for the study and analysis: for a thorough investigation of system performance and use of the suggested controllers, as well as tuning to use the new hybrid algorithm, the following scenarios are considered: the current rate of rising of the generator’s reference voltage under normal operating conditions is 10% an increase of 10% in the total busload on bus 3, taking into consideration the additional weight route 3, which carries moderate to heavy traffic conditions, has a three-point, six-cycle fault located near the middle of the line. Figures 5(a) to (d) illustrate the rotor speed deviations of the most afflicted generator in each fault scenario. Figure 5(a) depicts the rotor speed

deviation of a generator with an MG penetration level of 50 MW, Figure 5(b) depicts the rotor speed deviation of a generator with an MG penetration level of 30 MW, Figure 5(c) depicts the rotor speed deviation of a generator with an MG penetration level of 50 MW, and Figure 5(d) depicts the rotor speed deviation of a generator with an MG penetration level of 10 MW.

Figure 5. The most impacted generator's rotor speed deviations in each fault condition; (a) 50 MW MG, (b) 30 MW MG, (c) 50 MW MG, and (d) 10 MW

4. CONCLUSION

This study provides the basis for a brand-new PSS-based fraction-order type-2 innovation for a power grid for resistant context specific with renewable energy sources (RES) (sustainable energy sources) centre MG saturation. By integrating the complex genetic algorithm with the foraging algorithm bacteria, the type-2 FoPID controller optimises the limitations. The controller surpasses traditional PIDs and FoPID fractional order stabilisers that are proportionately integrated and are quicker with a high-quality resolution. Type 2 fuzzy FoPIDPSS also expressions high force characteristics in terms of variable variation in the penetrating MG power system. As seen in the nonlinear simulation results, the fractional parameter impact has an impact on the system's optimal dynamic output under several perturbed circumstances and disruption ambiguities. To show its dominance, the type-2 fuzzy FoPIDPSS is likened to the other 3 types of PID-based PSSs. The low point values of the ITSE and ITAE indices also demonstrate the type-2 fuzzy FoPIDPSS's optimal efficiency. According to this quantitative assessment, the planned controller overtakes the conventional PIDPSS controller in terms of efficient weakening of oscillations and reducing resolving time. This study provides the basis for a brand-new PSS-based fraction-order type 2 innovation for a power system for resistant context specific with RES (sustainable renewable resources) centre MG saturation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors thank the editor and the anonymous reviewers for their insightful feedback, which helped to improve the clarity and significance of our paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. A. de S. Ribeiro, O. R. Saavedra, S. L. de Lima, and J. G. de Matos, "Isolated micro-grids with renewable hybrid generation: the case of Lençóis Island," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, Jan. 2010, doi: 10.1109/TSTE.2010.2073723.
- [2] J. Farfan and C. Breyer, "Structural changes of global power generation capacity towards sustainability and the risk of stranded investments supported by a sustainability indicator," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 141, pp. 370–384, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.09.068.
- [3] S. Kakran and S. Chanana, "Smart operations of smart grids integrated with distributed generation: A review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 81, pp. 524–535, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2017.07.045.
- [4] N. M. Kumar, "Blockchain: enabling wide range of services in distributed energy system," *Beni-Suef University Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 701–704, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.bjbas.2018.08.003.
- [5] P. K. Wong, H. C. Wong, C. M. Vong, Z. Xie, and S. Huang, "Model predictive engine air-ratio control using online sequential extreme learning machine," *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 79–92, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.1007/s00521-014-1555-7.
- [6] M. R. Miveh, M. F. Rahmat, A. A. Ghadimi, and M. W. Mustafa, "Power quality improvement in autonomous microgrids using multi-functional voltage source inverters: a comprehensive review," *Journal of Power Electronics*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 1054–1065, Jul. 2015, doi: 10.6113/JPE.2015.15.4.1054.
- [7] L. Zhu, H. Shi, and M. Ding, "A chaotic BP neural network used to wind power prediction," in *2018 2nd IEEE Advanced Information Management, Communicates, Electronic and Automation Control Conference (IMCEC)*, IEEE, May 2018, pp. 1169–1172, doi: 10.1109/IMCEC.2018.8469532.
- [8] P. C. Pradhan, R. K. Sahu, and S. Panda, "Firefly algorithm optimized fuzzy PID controller for AGC of multi-area multi-source power systems with UPFC and SMES," *Engineering Science and Technology, an International Journal*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 338–354, Mar. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.jestch.2015.08.007.
- [9] N. M. Kumar, K. Sudhakar, and M. Samykano, "Performance evaluation of CdTe BIPV roof and façades in tropical weather conditions," *Energy Sources, Part A: Recovery, Utilization, and Environmental Effects*, vol. 42, no. 9, pp. 1057–1071, May 2020, doi: 10.1080/15567036.2019.1602216.
- [10] P. Saravanan, N. M. Kumar, M. Ettappan, R. Dhanagopal, and J. Vishnupriyan, "Effect of exhaust gas re-circulation on performance, emission and combustion characteristics of ethanol-fueled diesel engine," *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*, vol. 20, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.csite.2020.100643.
- [11] M.-B. Li, G.-B. Huang, P. Saratchandran, and N. Sundararajan, "Fully complex extreme learning machine," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 68, pp. 306–314, Oct. 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.neucom.2005.03.002.
- [12] J. Z. Shi, "A fractional order general type-2 fuzzy PID controller design algorithm," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 52151–52172, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2980686.
- [13] H. M. Jabr, D. Lu, and N. C. Kar, "Design and implementation of neuro-fuzzy vector control for wind-driven doubly-fed induction generator," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 404–413, Oct. 2011, doi: 10.1109/TSTE.2011.2160374.
- [14] M. Ren, J. Zhang, Y. Tian, and G. Hou, "A neural network controller for variable-speed variable-pitch wind energy conversion systems using generalized minimum entropy criterion," *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, pp. 1–9, 2014, doi: 10.1155/2014/412027.
- [15] L. Luo *et al.*, "Optimal scheduling of a renewable based microgrid considering photovoltaic system and battery energy storage under uncertainty," *Journal of Energy Storage*, vol. 28, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.est.2020.101306.
- [16] O. Hafez and K. Bhattacharya, "Optimal design of electric vehicle charging stations considering various energy resources," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 107, pp. 576–589, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2017.01.066.
- [17] V.-H. Bui, A. Hussain, and H.-M. Kim, "Double deep Q-learning-based distributed operation of battery energy storage system consider," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 457–469, 2019.
- [18] A. Chatterjee, A. Keyhani, and D. Kapoor, "Identification of photovoltaic source models," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 883–889, 2011, doi: 10.1109/TEC.2011.2159268.
- [19] Y. Li, S. Q. Mohammed, G. S. Nariman, N. Aljojo, A. Rezvani, and S. Dadfar, "Energy management of microgrid considering renewable energy sources and electric vehicles using the backtracking search optimization algorithm," *Journal of Energy Resources Technology, Transactions of the ASME*, vol. 142, no. 5, 2020, doi: 10.1115/1.4046098.
- [20] F. Najibi, T. Niknam, and A. Kavousi-Fard, "Optimal stochastic management of renewable MG (micro-grids) considering electro-thermal model of PV (photovoltaic)," *Energy*, vol. 97, pp. 444–459, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2015.12.122.
- [21] Q. Sun, D. Xing, H. Alafnan, X. Pei, M. Zhang, and W. Yuan, "Design and test of a new two-stage control scheme for SMES-battery hybrid energy storage systems for microgrid applications," *Applied Energy*, vol. 253, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.113529.
- [22] F. Dawood, G. M. Shafiullah, and M. Anda, "Stand-alone microgrid with 100% renewable energy: A case study with hybrid solar pv-battery-hydrogen," *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, vol. 12, no. 5, 2020, doi: 10.3390/su12052047.
- [23] H. K. Abdulkhader, J. Jacob, and A. T. Mathew, "Robust type-2 fuzzy fractional order PID controller for dynamic stability enhancement of power system having RES based microgrid penetration," *International Journal of Electrical Power and Energy Systems*, vol. 110, pp. 357–371, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.ijepes.2019.03.027.
- [24] G. Abitova, V. Nikulin, L. Rzayeva, T. Zadenova, and A. Myrzatay, "Neural network modeling of agglomeration firing process for polymetallic ores," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 4352–4363, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i4.pp4352-4363.
- [25] H. Arshada, S. A. Zulkiflia, and M. H. Khan, "Adaptive filter algorithms for state of charge estimation methods: A comprehensive review," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 1360–1367, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v26.i3.pp1360-1367.

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